

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL AND RELIGIOUS-POLITICAL ENVIRONMENT IN THE PERIOD OF MUTANABBI'S LIFE

Aliyev J.

The senior teacher of the chair "Russian and Eastern languages"
Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan

Mammadova Z.

The senior teacher of the chair "Russian and Eastern languages"
Nakhchivan State University, Azerbaijan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054985>

Abstract

Abu-al-Tayyab Ahmad bin Husain known as Al-Mutanabbi is a very famous Arabic poet from the Abbasid period. He was born in 915 AD in Kufa, Iraq and died in 965 AD. He was the court poet of Saif-al-Daulah of Aleppo for whom he composed most of his poems. This is Mutanabbi whose poems keep Saif-al-Daulah alive in the history of the Arab world. Al-Mutanabbi composed his best poems for him. Al-Mutanabbi is one the greatest, most prominent and influential poets of Arabic language. His poetry has been translated into several important languages of the world. Although his poetry largely comprises the odes in praise of the kings, viziers, and governors he visited during his lifetime, his greatness lies in his sharp intelligence and wittiness. He was very talented and a genius. In his poetry he has discussed topics of philosophy of life, the courage which was so favourite to Arab poets, and the description of battles. When he used to write satires, it would be very painful for the person it was intended for. One of the best examples of this type of poetry is a satirical poem which he composed in the satire of Kafur Ikhshidi, the king of Egypt. He uses beautiful similes and metaphors in his poetry. Al-Mutanabbi is one of the very popular poets of Arabic and his poems are still widely popular in the Arab world.

Keywords: Al-Mutanabbi, religion, politics, religious views, arab poetry, poet, poetry

Al-Mutanabbi, who is considered one of the leading poets of classical Arabic literature (the poet's full name is Abu al-Tayyib al-Mutanabbi Ahmad ibn al-Huseyn ibn al-Hasan ibn Abd al-Samad al-Jufi al-Kindi al-Kufi - J.A.). m. He was born in 915 in a poor family in al-Kinda neighborhood of Kufa city. His father was a water carrier. Al-Mutanabbi's upbringing in a center of science and culture like Kufa played a major role in his formation as a comprehensive personality and a wise person. The poet received his first education right here - in Kufa, in the madrasa taught by Shiite scholars. Most medieval researchers report that al-Mutanabbi wrote poetry from childhood and had a wonderful speech. The life and work of Mutanabbi, who is considered a great representative of classical Arabic poetry, coincides with the third stage of Arabic literature characterized as the period of stabilization of literary synthesis traditions during the Abbasid period (750-1258).

Mutanabbi's entire life coincided with an environment of internal and external political strife, and the turbulent environment did not leave an impact on the poet's creativity. As for Al-Mutanabbi's religious and political views, different and even contradictory opinions are expressed in the sources. Opinions surrounding his arrest are radically different. Some claim that he was arrested because he led a popular uprising for his political actions, while others claim that he was arrested because of his claim to be a prophet.

Al-Badi, the author of a tazkirah, which is the source of the most wrong ideas about Al-Mutanabbi, narrates the words of Abu Abdullah Muaz ibn Ismail, who lived at that time: "Abu al-Tayyib h. He was still

young when he came to Lazigiya (Latakia, a city in Syria – J.A) in 320 AD (932 J.A). When I got acquainted with his beautiful eloquence and eloquence, I welcomed him with a treat. I wanted to sit in a corner and listen to his impressions of the places where he was, to get to know his literature and knowledge more closely. I said to him: "You are a virtuous and dignified young man who has managed to associate with great and powerful rulers and win their patronage!" - I greeted with the words. But as soon as I finished speaking, he answered me in a bitter way: "Woe to you, do you realize what you are saying, do you know what you are talking about? I am chosen, my messenger"... Having said this, he recited his "Quran" consisting of 114 surahs by heart and performed a miracle to prove his prophethood..." [1, p. 28]. Khatib al-Baghdadi, another tazkirahist, points to this in his work entitled "Tarikh" and writes in his own language what al-Tanukhin told his father, Abu Ali ibn Abu Hamid: was". Most likely, the words called "verses" by the people of Aleppo and presented as "Al-Mutanabbi's Qur'an" in some source studies are saj (in classical literature, the weight of poetry determined by the precise anticipation of the sequence of long and short syllables in certain combinations that creates a beautiful reading rhythm in all verses - J.A.) is nothing but a sermon in the form. Whether they really belong to al-Mutanabbi or not is doubtful." Continuing after that, Abu Abdullah claims that al-Mutanabbi invited him to the desert and was able to stop the rain for a while and convinced those who witnessed this event that he was the Messenger of God. I.M. Filshinsky reports that such miracles are often performed by the Bedouins of

Yemen and that they use seven special spells for this [2, p.30].

Another researcher, Hasan al-Zayyat, who said that al-Mutanabbi made prophetic claims, claims that this event took place in 321 AH (933 AD) and to confirm what he said, he refers to such a narration circulating in languages at that time: "Allegedly, Abu al-Tayyib was asked about Prophet Muhammad (s.a.s), the poet replied: "He is a human race who brought news of my prophethood", - "There is no prophet after me." I am called "la" in the heavens. Most likely, the author took this wrong information from "Subh al-Munabbi". Al-Samani, one of the medieval authors, narrates the above-mentioned: "In the desert of Abu al-Tayyib al-Samawa, gathering around him a large number of supporters from Banu Kalb, Banu Kilab, Banu Saba (Sabaa) and other neighboring tribes, he first established himself as an Alawite, then the prophet announced. But very soon the people of Damascus saw the lies in his calls and claims, and sent a message to the Emir of Homs, al-Lulu ibn Ali al-Hashimi. The emir attacked al-Mutanabbi's group with his troops, killed many of his associates and exiled the rest. He sentenced Abu al-Tayyib to a long prison term. Al-Mutanabbi, who was under the personal control of al-Lulu, was released only after he signed a written document and admitted that he was wrong in his claim of prophethood and repented and returned to Islam" [3, p.506]. Al-Badi, confirming what al-Samani said, says that after the rumor about the poet's prophethood spread to the world, ibn Ali al-Hashimi arrested him in a village called Kutak and put shackles of willow on his neck. Al-Mutanabbi points to this in his ode and says:

"The governor of Kutak informed me that he is a descendant of Hashim ibn Abd Manaf. I answered him: "From the day you came from their descendants, their shackles were made of willow" (translated by J.A.).

Al-Askilani cites Ali ibn Mansur's letter to Abu Ala al-Ma'ari as the main source that proves the authenticity of this fact. The letter contains the following information: "Al-Mutanabbi was arrested and imprisoned during the reign of Ali ibn Isa." Abu al-Tayyib, who was brought before the ruler, confessed that he declared himself a prophet, and for that he was given fifty lashes. Al-Askilani mentions in his work the dialogue of Ghazi ibn Umm al-Shaybani with al-Mutanabbi as confirmation of what Ali ibn Mansur said. It is said that one day when Sheikh Abu al-Tayyib was asked about the meaning of his nickname, he related it to an insignificant, not very important event, but he did not want to reveal the reason because he was ashamed.

Giorgi Zeidan, a scholar of classical period Arabic literature and Islamic history, attributes al-Mutanabbi's arrest to political motives. The author says that when he was still a teenager (at the age of 17-18 - J.A.), he claimed to be a judge and gathered many supporters around him. Another researcher, Hasan al-Zayyat, says that the ambitious young man attracted people around him with his excellent oratorical skills, eloquent speeches and the magic of his sermons. Another author, Abu Nasr Abdul Malik al-Saalibi, also expresses this opinion. According to the witnesses, the young poet

finds fame so quickly that the ruling circles are worried about it. Not long after, the governor succeeded in arresting the young poet Ahmed. But the poet, taking refuge in the governor's mercy, sent him the following ode along with the letter: "I turn to you in despair. Death is as close to me as my coronary artery. I am begging you. Because trouble has already overwhelmed me. My knees do not bend from the weight of the iron (handcuffs - J.A.)."[4].

Complaining that the handcuffs were too heavy for a young man like him and that he could not prostrate while praying, al-Mutanabbi begged the governor for forgiveness. However, as soon as he is freed, the arrogant poet not only abandons his political ideas, but even goes further, claims to be an Alawite, and then to be a prophet, and calls people to believe in him. Hassan al-Zayyat and George Zeidan claim that al-Mutanabbi was arrested twice. However, it is not indicated in other investigated sources. The only source is a collection of articles about al-Mutanabbi, where it is shown that after his return to Kufa, he participated in the uprising against the government and called the people to fight for their desires, as well as being arrested for being an Alawite. Most likely, al-Mutanabbi was among those arrested during the suppression of the rebellion. If we refer to this assumption, the fact that he was arrested twice is justified. It should be noted that most researchers confirm the fact that al-Mutanabbi was arrested for his political actions and for leading the popular uprising. Sources date this event to about h. They indicate that it happened in the years 323-324 (AD 934-935 – J.A) with the date (4). While the poet was still in Lazigiya, the German researcher Blasher together with the people of al-Samawa desert m. He says that in 932 he took part in the Qarmati rebellion against the country's government, but the rebellion was suppressed very soon and al-Mutanabbi was arrested along with other participants. This fact is confirmed by Carl Brokelman, Wen Chin Ouyang, Omar Farrukh, Martin Nick and others. Ahmed Subhi al-Mutanabbi confirms that he received his nickname "as a memory of his life as a prisoner."

Al-Mutanabbi's Arab self-esteem and Arab bigotry were already formed at a young age. The pride and arrogance typical of real Arabs of the patriotic poet, who did not want to come to terms with the domination of the Persians over the Arabs and the presence of non-Arabs in power, came from here. Omar Farrukh narrates the arrest of the poet as follows: "Al-Mutanabbi's rebellious speech, who gathered the people near Homs and called them to refuse to pay taxes, soon reached the governor and he arrested the poet. Abu al-Tayyib received the nickname "Mutanabbi" after that. Shauqi states that the rebellion in which Dayf al-Mutanabbi participated was not a religious or a Qarmatian rebellion, as some researchers claim, but a purely political and popular rebellion. According to him, this event h. It happened at the end of the year 321 (around AD 933 – J.A). At that time, Abu al-Tayyib was not yet 20 years old. The poet, who did not hide his regret in the face of the disgrace and humiliation of his time, said: "I am the one with my help God explains the dignity of people", most likely

he tried to describe himself not as a prophet, but as an imam calling people to the right path. In this regard, one cannot disagree with the opinions of Abu Ala al-Maari, al-Ukbari, Khatib al-Baghdadi, ibn al-Anbari and other researchers. Authors who explain al-Mutanabbi's prophetic claims from a political point of view associate it with the poet's patriotism. It is no coincidence that Ibn al-Asir, who is considered the author of valuable works on the history of Islam, does not mention him among those who declared himself a prophet.

As for false prophecy in the history of Islam, its roots go back to the early years of Islam. As is known, in the seventh century in Arabia, Hazrat Along with Muhammad (pbuh), many others declared themselves prophets. Musaylim, the head of the Hanifa tribe in Yemen, Sajjah from the Tamim tribe, al-Aswad from the Khubban valley, Ibn Sayyad of Jewish origin in Medina, and others declared themselves the prophets of their time [5, p. 34]. Sources contain some information about them, albeit very little. Most of them lived during the time of Prophet Muhammad (s.a.v) and their political activities were led by Hazrat. They started near the end of the life of the prophet Muhammad (s.a.v). However, these people started their preaching activities as clergy much earlier. There are certain reasons for false prophecy and the fact that these prophets are mostly poets. As is known, words, poetry and poetry have a great value in Arab culture. In Arab culture, poets were held in high esteem, and their eloquence was even considered the strength of the tribe they belonged to. It is no coincidence that during the war, before the battle, the Arabs used to exchange words and exchange poems on the battlefield. These poems in the Rajaz genre were recited by a poet representative of the tribe or a warrior with a talent for poetry. And sometimes it happened that the winner of the competition of poetry and words was declared the winner of the battle without fighting. The poets who have special respect in Arabic literature have a place in the society and have influence due to their fame. It was precisely for this reason that God Almighty They claimed that the Messenger of God was a poet, likening the "Holy Qur'an" revealed to Prophet Muhammad (s.a.v) to a poem due to the rhythmic and harmonious language. Surahs and verses were revealed by Allah for the rejection of these claims. Thus, several verses of "Shu'ara" surah and "Ya sin" surah of "Quran-Karim" were revealed to prove that Prophet Muhammad (s.a.v) was a poet and what he said was not poetry.

It is likely that al-Mutanabbi's leadership of the people's uprising and raising his followers against the non-Arab authorities made people believe in his prophethood. On the other hand, Abu al-Tayyib's eloquent words in the form of his claims to be a judge and the declaration of himself as a judge who would unite all Arabs under a single administration made people believe that his sermons and speeches were extraordinary and magical. Emirs and caliphs were considered God's messengers on earth, his representatives. Perhaps it is for this reason that young Abu al-Tayyib's claims to judgeship earned him the nickname "Mutanabbi" (the one who pretends to be a

prophet - J.A.). It is no coincidence that Western authors explain this nickname of the poet not as "one who pretends to be a prophet", but as "who wants to be a prophet", "aspires to be a prophet". If we take into account that the unusualness is characteristic only of prophets, we can understand that it is no coincidence that the people call his sermons verses of the Koran, and himself a prophet. This point of view is consistent with what Ibn Jinni, al-Andalusi, Muzaffar al-Tabsi and others have said, who defend the idea that al-Mutanabbi declared himself a prophet in poetry. This can be explained by al-Mutanabbi's "game of prophecy" simply because he wanted to give his words and poems divinity and eternity. It is no coincidence that al-Mutanabbi himself said that he was sent to poets as a prophet and that his miracles were verses. Referring to the poet's contemporaries, Ibn Rashiq al-Qairavani states that Abu al-Tayyib said "I first prophesied in poetry..." [6, p.34]. Abul Qasim Muzaffar al-Tabsi, the author of one of the famous eulogies written on the death of al-Mutanabbi, says: "He declared himself a prophet in poetry, but his miracles were revealed in meanings."

Abu Muhammad Abdul Jalil ibn Wahab(un) al-Andalusi, one of the prominent representatives of classical Arabic-Spanish literature: "It is not surprising that he declared himself a prophet in poetry. I wish he knew that you are reciting his poem to raise your name and to be proud of others", he confirms the above opinion. Al-Saalibi also expresses the opinion that al-Mutanabbi's powerful eloquence and eloquence, the magic of his words made people believe in his extraordinariness and attracted them to him.

True, there are many who are sure that he got this nickname because of his excessive arrogance and desire to have great virtue, because he was not satisfied with the fame he achieved in the field of poetry, and because he aspired to the mastery achieved by victory. However, Joseph Hashim, one of the well-known researchers of classical Arabic literature, disagrees with these statements. According to him, this person, who has a beautiful speaking ability and a pure and fragile heart, was elevated by the age itself and made him the greatest genius of his age. Al-Mutanabbi's inner fire, crazy poetic nature sometimes forced him to praise undeserving people, which the poet figuratively expressed as "selling poetry in the market where cynicism prevails". At-Tabsi did not exaggerate at all when he said: "His personality has a supreme majesty, and his arrogance is typical of sultans." We think that none of the narrations spread about al-Mutanabbi's prophethood are nothing more than hearsay and gossip, not based on substantial evidence or proof. Al-Mutanabbi: "The whole universe is the narrator of my poems. If I say a poem, time itself will begin to repeat it" "Even the deaf hear my words, even the blind see my manners", "The horse, the night, the desert know me, the battle, the blow, the paper and the pen are familiar to me (my power)" - In fact, the verses in the form are nothing but a self-affirmation sign of an arrogant poet's genius, who is constantly faced with sarcasm and mockery due to his origin, a debased person burning with the desire for heroism [7, p.550].

It should be noted that al-Mutanabbi considered himself innocent and explained his arrest as the betrayal of the Jews:

"My place in the land of Nakhla is like the place of Prophet Jesus among the Jews. I live in such a nation that - may God himself punish them! - Just as the righteous prophet was a stranger among the people of Thamud, so I am a stranger" [8, p.71]. It is worth noting here that this verse is based on the poetic figure of talmih. Here, verses 11, 12, 14 and 15 of Surah al-Shams of the Holy Quran are pointed out: "Thamud (his people) rejected (Prophet Saleh) because of their perversion. When the most despicable of them got up (to kill the camel that God brought out of the rock as a miracle), the Prophet of God said to them: "Do not touch this she-camel of God, do not prevent her from drinking water!" But they considered Saleh a liar and caught the camel and slaughtered it. Because of these sins, God cut off their roots and destroyed them..." (Sura al-Shams, verses: 11-12, 14-15).

In this poem, Al-Mutanabbi compares his situation with Prophet Jesus, who appeared among the Jews, and Prophet Saleh, who was sent as a messenger to the people of Thamud. The poet says that he, like Jesus and Prophet Salih, was exposed to the body of people and was branded as a liar. Most likely, Jews did not play a positive role in the life of the poet. Joseph Hashim also confirms that Al-Mutanabbi's arrest was the result of political reporting and that Jewish priests were involved in this case. Al-Badi'i states that the poet alludes to this in several places of his divan. Let's take a look at a part of his ode dedicated to the governor:

"O merciful emir! I am a poor stranger standing in front of you with my hands tied. A stranger whose mother sheds bloody tears when she remembers. If I have done wrong before I met you, I repent before you now. They gossip about me and try to slander me. I am a victim of these gossips and lies. My detractors are trying to portray me to you as a person with many flaws and defects."

It is no coincidence that in one of the gatherings organized near Hamdani ruler Seif al-Dawla, he asked the poet: "Is it true that they call you Ahmad al-Nabawi?" - when asked, Abu al-Tayyib stated that it was a fabrication of his villains who tried to defame him [9, p.221]. Ibn Jinni also confirms this fact. According to him, the villains who informed the ruler about the poet claimed that Abu al-Tayyib had gathered a large number of people around him, and his goal was to seize the territories under the ruler's control and power. This was the main reason for Al-Mutanabbi's arrest.

Abu Ala al-Maari claims that what is said about this is exaggerated, and explains al-Mutanabbi's prophecy from the concept that "all geniuses have quirks." There was no doubt that he was unusual. Most likely, the poet had extraordinary strength. It was said that while he was in Lazigiya, he healed the wound with mouthwash and even raised the dead. On the other hand, al-Mutanabbi's powerful eloquence and eloquence, the magic of his words convinced people of his unusualness and attracted them to him. Since the age of ignorance, there have been various beliefs about

poets having extraordinary power and the magic inherent in their poems. The German researcher Nöldek states that the poet of the period of ignorance was the prophet of his tribe, its leader in peacetime, and a knight-hero during war. I. Goldtsiyer confidently says that the term "shair" meant not only "poet" but also "seer" (priest - J.A.) at that time [10, p.149]. In the Arabic language, the root of the word "poet" is the verb "shaara", which means to hear and feel. It was not accidental that the owners of the pen were named in this way. The ancient Arabs often meant feeling supernatural forces by this word. According to the famous Arab philologist ibn Rashiq al-Qairavani, the poet got this name because he heard and felt what ordinary people did not know. In general, quirks are characteristic of all poets. The Arabs, who believed that the owner of the poems recited with a certain melody and rhyme were inspired and dictated by supernatural forces, believed that the poets also had extraordinary powers like priests, and even believed that they had a connection with demons. The metaphysical approach to poetry and the art of words, the sounding of rhyming poetic pieces as mystical prayers, introduced poets as a class with extraordinary power, like priests and diviners. The German poet Heyne expressed this idea in one of his works: "Man is the most magnificent and supreme of all living beings. And the poet is the most chosen and the highest of the human community" [11, p.13].

Prof. Aida Gasimova touches on this topic in her article "Attitude of Jahiliyat Arabs to poets and orators" and characterizes the unusual nature of the creative process and its connection with supernatural forces as an unusual case that often occurs in human history [13, p.17]. . Mendeleev, a famous Russian scientist, discovered the periodic system of elements in a dream, Walter Scott wrote "Ayvego" while unconscious, Italian composer G. Tartini claimed to have heard the famous sonata dedicated to the Devil, Ibn Sina was informed of the solution of many scientific issues in a dream. and his warning of future events in some of his poems [for example, in one poem he warned of the Mongol-Tatar campaigns and their disaster] can be considered a manifestation of this mystical connection. The Russian orientalist I. Y. Krachkovsky was the first to refute the opinions of some researchers who put forward the idea that Al-Mutanabbi claimed to be a prophet. Referring to older and more reliable sources, the critic came to the conclusion that the poet's activity was not religious, but political in nature, and the connection of his name with the root "أَنْب" was the result of public fabrication. Academician I.Y. Krachkovskii mostly refers to Abu Ali al-Farisi, a contemporary of al-Mutanabbi, in his assumptions. The researcher states that the author approaches this fact very cautiously and narrates the incident as "we have heard that they narrate like this in Aleppo". Blasher, Carl Brokelman, Shawqi Dayf, al-Isfahani, Joseph Hashim, Ahmad Tabbel, Ronald Nicholson, Omar Farrukh, Martin Nick and others also agreed with academician I. Y. Krachkovsky and stated that the words said about al-Mutanabbi's prophecy are not based on truth. . I.Y. Krachkovski believes that the

legends and fictions related to the poet's prophecy appeared due to his poetic use of the names of faith and prophet in his poems. Al-Saalibi, the author of "Yatimatu-d-dahr", referring to ibn al-Jinni, one of the first commentators of al-Mutanabbi's divan and a contemporary of the poet, states that al-Mutanabbi got his nickname because of the poem "My place in the land of Nakhla...". Let's take into account that the poet claimed that this pseudonym was attached to him in his ode, and that what was said about his prophethood was nothing but a rumor [12, p.16].

As for the totality of all the obtained information, it is possible to conclude that Mutanabbi's creativity was greatly influenced by his political views. The poet, who was known for his harsh speeches against the ruling circles of his time, also had rapprochements with various ruling forces from time to time. This is evident from the praise poems he wrote to some statesmen who lived at that time. But in general, the main line of Mutanabbi's creativity is the challenge against injustice, rebellion, and subjugation. Regarding Mutanabbi's prophethood issue, based on the information in the sources, we think that he never made such a claim. But we can say with certainty that Mutanabbi is truly the prophet of classical Arabic poetry.

References:

1. Al-Barqouqi Abdul Rahman. Explanation of the Diwan of Al-Mutanabbi: B. 4, Ijalid, Beirut: Dar Al-Kitab Al-Arabi

2. Filshtinsky I.M. History of Arabic Literature X -XVIII centuries Moscow: Nauka, 1991, 725 pp.

3. Sam`ami. Kitab al-ansab/Repr. In fasimile from the manuscript in the British Museum add. 23, 355. Leyden – London: E.J.Brill, 1912, 602 p

4. <http://biography.do>

5. Piotrovsky M.B. Prophetic movement in Arabia HIGH centuries. Islam / Religion. Society. State (collection of articles). Moscow: Nauka, 1994, pp. 19-

6. The world of Al-Mutanabbi. Poetry and wisdom. Afsana Mammadova, Baku-2011.

7. www.almeshkat.net/books/

8. Krachkovsky I.Yu. Selected works: In 6 vols. T. 2, Moscow-Leningrad: ed. Academy of Sciences of the USSR, 1956, 632 pp.

9. Ibn Al-Anbari Abu Al-Barakat Kamal Al-Din. Nuzhat Al-Albaa in the Layers of Literature / edited by Ibrahim Baghdad: Al-Andalus Press, 1970, 302 pages.

10. Rodionov M.A. Al-Mutanabbi: Poet in the Islamic Society/ Islam. Religion. Society. State (collection of articles). Moscow: Nauka, 1994, pp. 149-155

11. Gasimova A. Attitude of Jahiliyat Arabs to poets and orators // Issues of Eastern Philology, 2000, p. 11-31

12. Gasimova A. Arab-Muslim culture of the 10th century: historical necessity or divine tax? (Article II) // Scientific research, 2002, pp. 16-18

13. "The Holy Quran", (edited by) V. Mammadaliyev